

CO-DESIGN

This Co-Design phase includes two sub-phases:

1. Co-design of the data collection protocol

The first set of activities within the Co-Design phase should address the following four objectives:

- To provide participants with the necessary resources to autonomously assemble the Telraam sensor and/or to assist partners during an assembly workshop.
- To design the data collection protocol.
- To design the case study according to the participants' availability, skills, and expectations.
- To initially establish participants' commitment.

2. Co-design project (and data) governance

This second sub-phase specifically focuses on the project governance, i.e. what roles and responsibilities are assigned within the case study. It is noted that a key contribution to this stage is given, if used, by the Collaborative Pilot Schedule tool. Therefore, two key objectives were established for this phase: (1) establish a final case study governance framework in terms of roles, decision rights and accountabilities of each individual / entity involved; and (if case study leaders decide to include additional sensing technologies to Telraam) (2) make sure participants understand and agree upon what data they share and under what conditions. Regarding the latter, we believe that clarifying these aspects increases the level of trust between the partner and the participating citizens, besides underpinning a significant learning curve on data governance more generally from participating citizens.